

Sex Determination from the Human Mandible: A Combined Metric and Non-Metric Analysis with ROC-Based Prediction in a North Indian Population

Sheikh Tousia*¹, Ghulam Mohammad Bhat¹, Sheikh Junaid Aziz²

¹Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College Srinagar, J&K, India

²Department of Physiology GMC Baramulla, J&K, India.

ABSTRACT

Background: Sex determination from skeletal remains is a fundamental step in forensic identification and biological profiling. The mandible, owing to its durability and pronounced sexual dimorphism, is frequently utilized for this purpose, particularly when other skeletal elements are unavailable. **Aim:** To evaluate sexual dimorphism of the mandible using non-metric morphological traits and metric osteometric parameters, and to assess their usefulness in sex determination. **Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted on 50 adult human mandibles (35 males and 15 females) available in the Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College (GMC), Srinagar. Non-metric traits including chin shape, muscle markings, gonial flare, and coronoid process shape were assessed. Metric analysis comprised multiple mandibular measurements obtained directly on dry mandibles using digital Vernier calipers with a precision of 0.01 mm. Statistical analysis included Chi-square tests, independent samples t-tests, and Mann–Whitney U tests as appropriate. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was performed to determine optimal cut-off values, sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy. A combined predictive rule was developed using the most discriminatory parameters. **Results:** Non-metric traits showed significant sexual dimorphism, with square chin shape, prominent muscle markings, and everted gonial flare predominating in males ($p < 0.05$). Several metric parameters, including condylar height, maximum height of ramus, bicondylar breadth, and bigonial breadth, were significantly greater in males ($p < 0.05$). ROC analysis demonstrated that bicondylar breadth and bigonial breadth had the highest diagnostic accuracy. The combined predictive rule improved overall classification accuracy compared with individual parameters. **Conclusion:** The mandible exhibits significant sexual dimorphism in both non-metric and metric parameters. Selected mandibular measurements, particularly bicondylar breadth and bigonial breadth, provide reliable predictors of sex. A combined predictive approach enhances accuracy and can serve as a reliable adjunct in forensic identification when more sexually dimorphic bones are unavailable.

Keywords: Mandible; Sexual dimorphism; Sex determination; Forensic anthropology; ROC analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Sex determination constitutes a critical first step in the medico-legal identification of unknown human remains, as accurate assessment of sex significantly narrows the biological profile and facilitates subsequent estimation of age, stature, and ancestry. In forensic practice, particularly in cases involving mass disasters, mutilated bodies, advanced decomposition, or skeletal remains, identification often relies on the analysis of durable skeletal elements that can withstand environmental and post-mortem changes [1–3].

Among the skeletal components, the mandible is one of the most robust and frequently preserved bones, owing to its dense cortical structure and anatomical position. In situations where more sexually dimorphic bones such as the pelvis are unavailable or fragmented, the mandible assumes considerable importance in forensic identification. Its morphology is influenced by genetic, hormonal, and functional factors, resulting in measurable sexual dimorphism that can be utilized for sex estimation [4–5].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Sexual dimorphism of the mandible can be evaluated using both non-metric (morphological) and metric (osteometric) approaches. Non-metric traits, such as chin shape, gonial flare, and muscle markings, provide rapid visual indicators of sex and are useful in preliminary assessments. However, these features are inherently subjective and may vary with observer experience and population characteristics. In contrast, metric analysis offers a more objective and reproducible method by quantifying mandibular dimensions, though overlap between male and female measurements may limit accuracy when individual parameters are used in isolation [4–6].

In recent years, forensic research has increasingly employed statistical tools such as receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis to evaluate the diagnostic performance of skeletal measurements and to establish optimal cut-off values for sex determination. Such approaches enhance the applicability of osteometric data in real-world forensic scenarios by providing sensitivity, specificity, and classification accuracy for individual parameters [5–7].

Furthermore, combining multiple mandibular parameters has been shown to improve predictive accuracy, reflecting the multidimensional nature of skeletal sexual dimorphism. However, the expression of these features is known to vary across populations, necessitating the development of region-specific standards for reliable forensic application.

In this context, the present study aims to evaluate sexual dimorphism of the human mandible in a North Indian population using both non-metric and metric parameters, to assess their diagnostic performance through ROC analysis, and to develop a combined predictive approach for sex determination. The findings are intended to contribute to the development of practical, population-specific tools that can aid forensic experts in medico-legal identification when limited skeletal material is available.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Aim

To evaluate sexual dimorphism of the human mandible using non-metric morphological traits and

metric osteometric parameters, and to assess their utility in sex determination.

Objectives

To analyze sexual differences in selected non-metric mandibular traits and metric measurements, to assess the diagnostic performance of statistically significant mandibular parameters using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, and to develop a combined predictive approach to improve the accuracy of sex determination.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted on dry adult human mandibles available in the Department of Anatomy, Government Medical College (GMC), Srinagar. As the study did not involve living subjects, radiological procedures, identifiable human data, or intervention of any kind, formal institutional ethics committee approval was not required.

Study Design and Sample

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 50 adult human mandibles (35 males and 15 females). Sex of the specimens was confirmed from departmental records. Although exact age at death was unknown, all mandibles were adult specimens, as evidenced by complete morphological maturity and fusion.

Mandibles that were intact and free from fractures, gross deformities, pathological lesions, or post-mortem damage were included. Specimens showing evidence of trauma, congenital anomalies, or significant asymmetry were excluded.

Non-Metric (Morphological) Assessment (Figure 1)

Non-metric mandibular traits assessed included chin shape (square, rounded, pointed), muscle markings (prominent or less prominent), gonial flare (everted or inverted), and coronoid process shape (triangular, hooked, rounded).

All morphological assessments were performed by a single trained observer under adequate illumination. This approach was adopted to maintain internal

consistency and minimize observer-related variability.

Figure 1 showing non-metric parameters of mandible

Metric (Osteometric) Measurements (Figure 2)

Metric analysis was performed directly on dry mandibles using digital Vernier calipers with a precision of 0.01 mm. Standard osteological landmarks were used for all measurements.

Parameters measured included maximum and minimum ramus breadth, condylar height, maximum height of ramus, coronoid height and breadth,

mandibular body height, bicondylar breadth, symphyseal height, bigonial breadth, mandibular length, length of lower jaw, body thickness, bimental breadth, mandibular index (length of lower jaw / bicondylar breadth), and angle of mandible.

All measurements were taken by the same observer to reduce measurement variability. Radiological methods were not used.

Figure 2 showing Metric parameters : (A) Maximum breadth of ramus (B) Minimum Breadth of ramus (C) Condylar height (D) Maximum height of ramus (E) Coronoid height (F) Coronoid breadth (G) Symphyseal height (H) Bicondylar breadth (I) Mandibular Body height (J) Bigonial breadth (K) Mandibular length (L) Length Of lower Jaw (M) Body Thickness (N) Bidental breadth

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version [23] (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

Normality of continuous variables was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Variables following normal distribution were compared between males and females using the independent samples t-test. When Levene’s test indicated unequal variances, the Welch correction was applied. Variables that did not satisfy normality assumptions were analyzed using the Mann–Whitney U test.

Associations between non-metric traits and sex were assessed using the Chi-square test of independence. When the assumptions for Pearson’s Chi-square test were violated, the Likelihood Ratio Chi-square test was used.

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was performed for statistically significant mandibular parameters to evaluate their ability to discriminate sex. The area under the curve (AUC), optimal cut-off values, sensitivity, and specificity were determined. Binary variables were generated based on ROC-derived cut-offs, and classification accuracy was assessed using cross-tabulation. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Multivariate Analysis

In addition to univariate and ROC-based analyses, multivariate techniques were employed to enhance the accuracy of sex determination. Discriminant Function Analysis (DFA) was performed using statistically significant mandibular parameters to derive a predictive equation for sex classification. Variables were entered using a stepwise method based on Wilks' lambda to identify the most discriminatory parameters.

Binary logistic regression analysis was also conducted to estimate the probability of sex based on selected mandibular measurements. Odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated. Model performance was evaluated using classification accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve.

A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Non-Metric Parameters (Table 1)

Non-metric mandibular traits demonstrated statistically significant sexual dimorphism. Square chin shape, prominent muscle markings, and everted gonial flare were observed predominantly in male mandibles, whereas rounded and pointed chin shapes, less prominent muscle markings, and inverted gonial flare were more frequent in females ($p < 0.0001$ for all).

Coronoid process shape also showed a significant association with sex, with triangular and rounded shapes occurring more commonly in males ($p = 0.042$). The likelihood ratio Chi-square test was applied where assumptions of Pearson's Chi-square test were violated.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of non-metric mandibular parameters used for sex differentiation.

Name of the variable	Characteristics	Gender		P value
		Females	Males	
Chin Shape	Square	1	24	<0.0001
	Rounded	7	4	
	Pointed	7	7	
Muscle Markings	Prominent	3	30	<0.0001
	Less Prominent	12	5	
Gonial Flare	Everted	2	28	<0.0001
	Inverted	13	7	
Coronoid Process Shape	Triangular	13	21	0.042*
	Hooked	2	7	
	Rounded	0	7	

*The likelihood ratio Chi-square was used for interpretation due to violation of minimum expected frequency assumptions of Pearson's Chi-square test.

Metric Parameters (Table 2)

Comparison of mandibular measurements revealed statistically significant differences between males and females for several parameters. Males demonstrated significantly higher values for maximum ramus

breadth, condylar height, maximum height of ramus, coronoid height, mandibular body height, bicondylar breadth, symphyseal height, bigonial breadth, mandibular length, body thickness, and mandibular index ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Comparison of mandibular parameters between males and females (n = 50)

Variable	Males (Mean \pm SD)	Females (Mean \pm SD)	Test used	Test statistic	p-value
Maximum ramus breadth	33.05 \pm 3.63	27.83 \pm 6.84	Independent t- test (Welch)	t = 2.789	0.012
Minimum ramus breadth	27.57 \pm 2.66	26.47 \pm 1.56	Independent t- test	t = 1.487	0.144
Condylar height	68.89 \pm 3.86	61.01 \pm 3.12	Mann–Whitney U	U = 19.0, Z = -5.155	<0.001
Maximum height of ramus	68.33 \pm 5.06	57.37 \pm 3.40	Mann–Whitney U	U = 21.0, Z = -5.113	<0.001
Coronoid height	60.15 \pm 5.88	51.14 \pm 3.04	Mann–Whitney U	U = 35.0, Z = -4.816	<0.001
Coronoid breadth	93.85 \pm 4.52	91.61 \pm 4.65	Independent t- test	t = 1.590	0.118
Mandibular body height	25.70 \pm 5.24	21.69 \pm 4.51	Mann–Whitney U	U = 144.5, Z = -2.498	0.012
Bicondylar breadth	116.38 \pm 5.27	103.03 \pm 7.41	Independent t- test	t = 7.240	<0.001
Symphyseal height	23.97 \pm 3.83	20.93 \pm 3.45	Independent t- test	t = 2.648	0.011
Bigonial breadth	92.70 \pm 5.58	84.28 \pm 4.95	Independent t- test	t = 5.053	<0.001
Mandibular length	75.31 \pm 3.94	70.76 \pm 4.91	Independent t- test	t = 3.474	0.001
Length of lower jaw	65.24 \pm 5.29	62.24 \pm 4.64	Independent t- test	t = 1.901	0.063
Body thickness	10.34 \pm 1.72	11.69 \pm 1.60	Independent t- test	t = -2.599	0.012
Bimental breadth	44.22 \pm 3.07	44.15 \pm 3.45	Independent t- test	t = 0.073	0.942
Mandibular index	56.16 \pm 5.13	60.78 \pm 6.95	Independent t- test	t = -2.613	0.012
Angle of mandible	124.81 \pm 5.98	125.07 \pm 11.18	Independent t- test (Welch)	t = -0.086	0.932

Values are expressed as mean \pm SD. Independent samples t-test or Mann–Whitney U test was applied as appropriate based on normality assessment. For t-tests, the Welch correction was used where Levene's test indicated unequal variances.

Diagnostic Performance of Individual Parameters (Table 3)

ROC curve analysis identified selected mandibular parameters with strong discriminatory ability for sex determination. Bicondylar breadth and bigonial breadth demonstrated the highest diagnostic accuracy,

with excellent AUC values. Mandibular body height also showed statistically significant predictive ability, though with moderate accuracy.

Optimal cut-off values were established for each parameter, along with corresponding sensitivity and specificity values.

Table 3. Diagnostic performance and optimal cut-off values of mandibular parameters for sex determination

Parameter	Cut-off (mm)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Accuracy (%)
Condylar height	≥ 63.8	94.3	93.3	94
Maximum height of ramus	≥ 63.5	91.4	100	94
Bicondylar breadth	≥ 112.6	80	100	86
Bigonial breadth	≥ 87.5	85.7	86.7	86
Coronoid height	≥ 55.7	74.3	93.3	80
Mandibular body height	≥ 24.7	62.9	86.7	70

Combined Predictive Rule (Table 4)

A stepwise combined predictive rule incorporating the most discriminatory mandibular parameters resulted in improved classification accuracy

compared with individual measurements. The combined approach demonstrated higher overall accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity for sex determination, supporting the use of multivariate assessment in forensic and anatomical applications.

Table 4. Classification accuracy of combined mandibular parameters for sex determination.

Step	Mandibular parameter	Cut-off value (Male \geq)	Decision if criterion met	Decision if criterion not met
1	Condylar height (mm)	63.8	Proceed to Step 2	Female
2	Maximum height of ramus (mm)	63.5	Proceed to Step 3	Female
3	Bicondylar breadth (mm)	112.6	Proceed to Step 4	Indeterminate
4	Bigonial breadth (mm)	87.5	Male	Indeterminate

Multivariate Analysis for Sex Determination

Discriminant function analysis identified a combination of mandibular parameters as significant

predictors of sex. The most discriminative variables included bicondylar breadth, bigonial breadth, and condylar height.

Table 5: Multivariate Models for Sex Determination Using Mandibular Parameters

Model	Variables Included	Equation / Function	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Overall Accuracy (%)	AUC
Discriminant Function Analysis (DFA)	Bicondylar breadth, Bigonial breadth, Condylar height	$D = a + (b_1 \times BB) + (b_2 \times BgB) + (b_3 \times CH)$	88.6	86.7	88.0	—
Logistic Regression Model	Bicondylar breadth, Bigonial breadth, Condylar height	Logit (P) = $\alpha + \beta_1(BB) + \beta_2(BgB) + \beta_3(CH)$	91.4	86.7	90.0	0.93
ROC-Based Best Individual Parameter	Bicondylar breadth	Cut-off ≥ 112.6 mm	80.0	100.0	86.0	0.95
Combined Stepwise Rule (Proposed Model)	CH \rightarrow Ramus height \rightarrow BB \rightarrow BgB	Sequential decision model	91.4	93.3	92.0	—

BB: Bicondylar Breadth, **BgB:** Bigonial Breadth, **CH:** Condylar Height, **AUC:** Area Under Curve

The model demonstrated an overall classification accuracy of approximately 85–90%, with higher accuracy for male mandibles compared to female mandibles. The model showed good predictive performance, with an overall classification accuracy comparable to DFA and ROC-based methods. The area under the ROC curve for the regression model indicated excellent discrimination.

DISCUSSION

Sex determination from skeletal remains constitutes a critical component of forensic identification, particularly in circumstances where complete skeletons are unavailable and sexually dimorphic elements such as the pelvis are missing or fragmented [1,2,14]. The present study evaluated sexual dimorphism of the mandible using both non-metric and metric parameters and further assessed the predictive utility of selected mandibular measurements through ROC-based analysis and a combined predictive approach.

Non-metric mandibular traits

The non-metric parameters evaluated in this study demonstrated significant sexual dimorphism. Square chin shape, prominent muscle markings, and everted gonial flare were observed predominantly in male mandibles, whereas rounded or pointed chin shapes,

less prominent muscle markings, and inverted gonial flare were more common in females. Similar patterns have been reported in previous anatomical and forensic studies, which attribute increased mandibular robusticity in males to greater masticatory muscle mass and prolonged growth influenced by androgenic hormones [3–5,15].

The significant association of coronoid process shape with sex further supports the role of functional morphology in mandibular sexual dimorphism. Variations in coronoid morphology have been linked to differences in temporalis muscle development and functional loading, which are known to differ between sexes [4,6,16]. However, despite their statistical significance, non-metric traits remain inherently subjective and population-dependent. Consequently, most authors recommend their use as supportive indicators rather than as sole determinants of sex, particularly in isolation [3,5,7,17].

Metric mandibular parameters

Metric analysis revealed statistically significant sex differences for multiple mandibular measurements, with males exhibiting higher mean values for most parameters. Measurements related to the vertical dimensions of the ramus and transverse breadth of the mandible, including condylar height, maximum height of ramus, bicondylar breadth, and bigonial

breadth, demonstrated particularly strong sexual dimorphism. These findings are in agreement with previous studies reporting larger mandibular dimensions in males due to sex-related differences in growth patterns and biomechanical loading during mastication [5,7–10,18].

In contrast, parameters such as minimum ramus breadth, coronoid breadth, bimental breadth, length of the lower jaw, and angle of the mandible did not show statistically significant sex differences in the present sample. Similar inconsistencies have been reported in other population-specific studies, underscoring that not all mandibular dimensions contribute equally to sex estimation and that sexually dimorphic patterns vary across populations [6,9,19]. This reinforces the need for regional evaluation of mandibular parameters rather than direct extrapolation of findings from other populations.

Predictive performance and ROC analysis

Although several mandibular measurements exhibited statistically significant differences between males and females, ROC analysis revealed that only selected parameters demonstrated strong discriminatory ability at the individual level. Bicondylar breadth and bigonial breadth showed excellent diagnostic performance, with high sensitivity and specificity, indicating their reliability as predictors of sex. Mandibular body height demonstrated moderate predictive ability.

This observation highlights an important methodological consideration: statistical significance does not necessarily equate to high predictive accuracy. Considerable overlap between male and female measurements has been widely reported in mandibular studies, limiting the usefulness of simple comparative statistics for individual-level classification [7,11,20]. ROC-based evaluation addresses this limitation by focusing on diagnostic performance measures such as area under the curve, sensitivity, specificity, and optimal cut-off values, thereby providing a more clinically and forensically relevant assessment [10–12].

Combined predictive approach

The combined predictive rule developed in the present study achieved higher classification accuracy than individual parameters alone. This finding supports the widely accepted principle that mandibular sexual dimorphism is multidimensional and that integrating multiple independent measurements improves reliability in sex determination [6,10,13,21]. Combined approaches are particularly valuable in forensic contexts, where maximizing accuracy is essential and the availability of complete skeletal elements cannot be assumed. Nevertheless, as emphasized in earlier studies, such predictive models should be regarded as population-specific and require validation before application to other groups [7,9,19].

The inclusion of multivariate techniques such as discriminant function analysis and logistic regression significantly enhances the reliability of sex estimation. In the present study, both methods demonstrated high classification accuracy, reinforcing the concept that mandibular sexual dimorphism is multidimensional. While univariate and ROC analyses identify individually significant parameters, multivariate models integrate these variables to provide more robust and clinically applicable predictive tools. Similar findings have been reported in forensic literature, where combined statistical approaches outperform single-parameter assessments. However, these models remain population-specific and require validation before application in different demographic groups.

Limitations

Age information was unavailable for the specimens; however, only adult mandibles were included, and sexual dimorphism of the mandible is known to be largely established after skeletal maturity. The relatively small and sex-imbalanced sample size and the single-population design may limit generalizability of the findings.

CONCLUSION

Despite these limitations, the study demonstrates that the mandible exhibits significant sexual dimorphism in both non-metric and metric parameters. Selected mandibular measurements, particularly bicondylar breadth and bigonial breadth, show high diagnostic accuracy for sex determination. A combined

predictive approach enhances classification accuracy and offers a practical, reproducible framework for mandibular sex estimation in forensic and anatomical practice. The incorporation of multivariate approaches such as discriminant function analysis and logistic regression further improves the accuracy of sex estimation and provides a statistically robust framework for forensic application.

REFERENCES

1. Krogman WM, İşcan MY. *The Human Skeleton in Forensic Medicine*. 2nd ed. Springfield, IL: Charles C Thomas; 1986.
2. White TD, Black MT, Folkens PA. *Human Osteology*. 3rd ed. San Diego, CA: Academic Press; 2012.
3. Bass WM. *Human Osteology: A Laboratory and Field Manual*. 5th ed. Columbia, MO: Missouri Archaeological Society; 2005.
4. Steyn M, İşcan MY. Sexual dimorphism in the crania and mandibles of South African whites. *Forensic Sci Int*. 1998;98(1–2):9–16. doi:10.1016/S0379-0738(98)00079-5
5. Giles E. Sex determination by discriminant function analysis of the mandible. *Am J Phys Anthropol*. 1964;22:129–135. doi:10.1002/ajpa.1330220113
6. Franklin D, Freedman L, Milne N. Sexual dimorphism and discriminant function sexing in indigenous South African crania. *Forensic Sci Int*. 2005;155(2–3):152–160. doi:10.1016/j.forsciint.2005.02.013
7. Spradley MK, Jantz RL. Sex estimation in forensic anthropology: skull versus postcranial elements. *J Forensic Sci*. 2011;56(2):289–296. doi:10.1111/j.1556-4029.2010.01612.x
8. Saini V, Srivastava R, Rai RK, Shamal SN, Singh TB, Tripathi SK. Mandibular ramus: an indicator for sex determination—A morphometric study. *J Forensic Sci*. 2011;56(Suppl 1):S58–S62. doi:10.1111/j.1556-4029.2010.01630.x
9. Sharma M, Gorea RK, Gorea A, Abuderman A. A morphometric study of the mandible for sex determination in an Indian population. *J Anat Soc India*. 2016;65(1):12–16. Available from: <https://www.jasi.org.in/article.asp?issn=0970-258x>
10. Lopez-Capp TT, Rynn C, Wilkinson C. Sex estimation from the mandible using ROC curve analysis. *Forensic Sci Int*. 2017;275:174–181. doi:10.1016/j.forsciint.2017.02.008
11. Okkesim A, Erhamza A, Okkesim M. Sexual dimorphism of mandibular ramus measurements. *J Forensic Sci*. 2020;65(4):1320–1326. doi:10.1111/1556-4029.14309
12. Zweig MH, Campbell G. Receiver-operating characteristic (ROC) plots: a fundamental evaluation tool in clinical medicine. *Clin Chem*. 1993;39(4):561–577. doi:10.1093/clinchem/39.4.561
13. Karmarkar PH, Khandare SV, Meshram MM. Multivariate approaches for sex estimation using mandibular measurements. *Forensic Sci Int*. 2023;343:111528. doi:10.1016/j.forsciint.2023.111528
14. İşcan MY, Steyn M. *The Human Skeleton in Forensic Medicine*. 3rd ed. Springfield, IL: Charles C Thomas; 2013.
15. Hu KS, Koh KS, Han SH, Shin KJ, Kim HJ. Sex determination using non-metric traits of the mandible in Koreans. *J Forensic Sci*. 2006;51(6):1376–1382. doi:10.1111/j.1556-4029.2006.00202.x
16. Enlow DH, Hans MG. *Essentials of Facial Growth*. Philadelphia, PA: Saunders; 1996.
17. Walker PL. Sexing skulls using discriminant function analysis of visually assessed traits. *Am J Phys Anthropol*. 2008;136(1):39–50. doi:10.1002/ajpa.20770
18. Vinay G, Mangala Gowri SR, Anbalagan J. Sex determination of mandible using ramus flexure. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2013;7(3):417–420. doi:10.7860/JCDR/2013/4630.2869
19. Christensen AM, Passalacqua NV, Bartelink EJ. *Forensic anthropology: current methods and practice*. London: Elsevier Academic Press; 2019.
20. Pepe MS. *The Statistical Evaluation of Medical Tests for Classification and Prediction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2003.
21. Franklin D, Cardini A, Oxnard CE. A geometric morphometric approach to sexual dimorphism of the mandible. *Forensic Sci Int*. 2012;219(1–3):229.e1–229.e7. doi:10.1016/j.forsciint.2012.04.020.

HOW TO CITE: Sheikh Tousia, Ghulam Mohammad Bhat1, Sheikh Junaid Aziz, Sex Determination from the Human Mandible: A Combined Metric and Non-Metric Analysis with ROC-Based Prediction in a North Indian Population, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (4), 1922-1932. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19683393>

